
*Received: 13th March 2022**Revised: 19th April 2022**Accepted: 28th May 2022***SEARCH ENGINE OPTIMIZATION IMPETUS FOR ONLINE BUYING JUDGEMENT****DIVYA DWIVEDI AND DR. NEELU JHALA****ABSTRACT**

In the digital world this is one of the important aspect that all the activities are influences by the social media or various means of the advertisements. Due to various digital practices including search engine optimizations approaches it is very easy to make any product and visible to the audience. Making brand the product and advertising the same will gives significant effect on the consumer purchasing decisions. As we know that what we are viewing will be in our purchasing list. So there is predefine process to influence the customer and make them ready to purchase the projected product. This paper is an attempt to understand the reality behind this thought that search engine optimization influences the purchasing habits of the customer. Also the paper makes a decision on the same statement through statistical approach.

Keywords: digital, marketing, search engine, influences, decision, statistical.

INTRODUCTION

In the modern digital world which is also known as the world of online marketing or virtual marketing. The search of any kind of information, product and service searching are committed by the help of search engine. It is one of the necessary things which are associated with the search engine optimization that before utilizing search engine for a particular product and services searching there is need to make product brand through advertisements. The search engine optimization plays important role to computerized the advertisement and make it brand which is visible to the user during the searching of related data and also placed information in the first page. So, if information is available on the initial page of searching result then it may assume that search engine optimization approaches are influencing the thinking process of the user.

In the age of computer this is one of the significant facet that the entire doings are effects by the social media or several means of the announcements. In line for numerous virtual practices together with search engine optimizations methods, this is precisely easy to make somewhat product and noticeable to the audience. Forming brand, the making and advertising the similar will provides significant upshot on the consumer marketing decisions. It is well understood that what we are watching and what we are buying whether it is influenced by the search engine result or not. Thus there is a procedure which influences the consumer and make them mentally equipped for the procurement of projected product.

OBJECTIVE

The objective of the proposed case study is to identify the actual situation regarding influence of search engine optimization on the purchasing habits of the consumer. This objective has multiple section assessments like:

- 1) Assessing the influence of search engine optimization.
- 2) Assess the impact of branding which is produce by the help of search engine optimization approach.
- 3) Influence of social media marketing.

HYPOTHESIS:

Testing of hypothesis to assess that search engine optimization has a noteworthy impact on the consumers online buying judgement. At this time, we are inspecting that search engine marketing / digital marketing encouragements to the consumer to buying products / services online. **The null hypothesis framed for the supposition is:**

“Search engine optimization has a significant influence on the consumers’ online purchase decision”.

Alternate Hypothesis:

“Search engine optimization has not a significant influence on the consumers’ online purchase decision”.

Data and Analysis

In order to assess the opinion of the respondents about the noteworthy influence on the consumers’ online buying judgement over search engine optimization approaches. As the dataset, opinion of the respondents was gathered via a minor survey question set / variables to evaluate equally the variables. The question set to assess the hypothesis are:

- The SEO has a noteworthy influence on the consumers’ online buying conclusion.
- Advertisement which is shown on the initial page are grasping additional attention.

The evaluation of opinion of respondents regarding above mentioned variable / question were investigating for the resemblance or for important connection amid them. There are 300 responses are considered as the size of the data for both the variables. The analysis of the opinions of both variables is given below.

The analysis of the opinions of both variable / questions samples is given below. As per size of dataset and nature of data it is found that applying “z” on both the variable will be one of the best suitable test to find out the expected outcome here.

Question / Variables	N	Mean	z	Result
The SEO has a noteworthy influence on the consumers’ online buying conclusion.	300	3.82	0.189	Significant
Advertisement which is shown on the initial page are grasping additional attention.	300	3.84		

Table 1: SEO influence on the consumers online buying judgement

Detail Consequences:

According to test applied and above mentioned table some important statistical facts are taken in the considerations which are as follows:

‘Z’ Critical One Tail Value on 0.05 = 1.65

The considered figure of 300 samples are recorded for both the variable separately. Sighted the degree of dataset, it is obvious that “z” test is the suitable test to examine the hypothesis in the best suitable manner.

Analysis Data:

- Sample Size : 300
- The calculated value of z : 0.189
- The critical one tail value of z : 1.65
- The critical two tail value of z : 1.97
- The Level of significance : 0.05 or 5%

According to table, it is observed that the ‘z’ test applied on the responses received from the respondents. To test the statement, we consider the critical one tail value of “z” test for 0.05 level of significance which is 1.65.

It is find that the calculated value of ‘z’ is 0.189, which is a lesser than the one tail critical value of ‘z’ at, 0.05 level. So here it is found that hypothesis for the study is accepted and therefore alternative hypothesis is rejected. Consequently, by means of the receipt of null hypothesis we can say that search engine optimization has a noteworthy influence on the consumers’ online buying judgement.

Figure -1: SEO influence on the consumers online buying judgement

According to figure 1, the central tendency measurement of both the variable also depicts that there is great similarity in the opinion received by the respondents for both questions / variables. The observed central values 3.82 and 3.84 shows that the numerical average of the opinion of the 300 respondents are almost equal it means respondents are equally supporting both the statement which is good sign of stability of the statement. Finally, we can say that the people are acquainted with this fact and they know very well about this. With the closer inspection of the central tendency of data (mean) of the opinion of the respondents it is establish that there is no gap among the opinion of responder for both of the variables.

CONCLUSION

In the rapid running age of information technology, the big part of decision of our daily life is also depend on the results produced by the search engine. We are almost utilizing the search engine to get information about the product and services, its availability, price and delivery. From the study it is found that people are influence by the same and that are believing in the result received by the search engine. From the study it is clear that search engine optimization has a significant influence on the consumers' online purchase decision". It gives effect on the buying behavior of the consumer towards the online purchasing. There is lot of factor which are supported by the online marketing including availability of product, one click detail, pricing comparisons, discount, offers and home delivery. So as the conclusion it is find that search engine optimization has a significant influence on the consumers' online purchase decision".

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